

Conductometric and Spectrophotometric Studies on Cerium(IV)-, Praseodymium(III)- and Gadolinium(III)- 2,2'-Bipyridyl and 2,2',2''-Tripyridyl Complexes

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Manuscript received 9 August 1982, revised 24 December 1983, accepted 9 March 1984

The chelating behaviour of 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy) and 2,2',2''-tripyridyl (tripy) have been studied with Ce^{4+} , Pr^{3+} and Gd^{3+} spectrophotometrically at pH 1.5-11.0 and by conductometric titration and conductometric measurement. 2,2'-Bipyridyl and 2,2',2''-tripyridyl are recommended as suitable reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of Ce, Pr and Gd and form complexes of the types 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 at variable pH. The order of increasing stability constant is $Pr^{3+} > Ce^{4+} > Gd^{3+}$ -bipy $> Pr^{3+} > Ce^{4+} > Gd^{3+}$ -tripy (1 : 1). The free energy changes ($\Delta^{\circ}G$) of the complexes are determined.

Ce^{4+} , Pr^{3+} and Gd^{3+} formed organometallic compounds with cyclopentadienyl ring containing compounds¹. Ce- and Pr-methyl thymol blue² complexes were studied spectrophotometrically. Pr and Gd complexes were also studied spectrophotometrically using alizarin red S³ and chromatographically using hexafluoro acetyl acetone⁴. 2,2'-Bipyridyl was also used as a complexing agent for the spectrophotometric and conductometric studies⁵⁻⁷ of V, Nb, Ta, Mn, Cr, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg.

Experimental

$1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Ce(IV), Pr(III) and Gd(III)⁸; $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ 2,2'-bipyridyl and 2,2',2''-tripyridyl⁹ solutions were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amounts of $Ce(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, Pr_2O_3 , Gd_2O_3 (Merck, A.R., 99.9%), 2,2'-bipyridyl and 2,2',2''-tripyridyl (Riedel de Haen), respectively in suitable solvents. Buffer solutions of pH 1.5-11.3 were prepared according to standard methods¹⁰.

Pye Unicam Model 290 MK2 pH Meter, Pye Unicam SP 8000 Ultraviolet Recording spectrophotometer, and Solu Bridge REG.US PAT OFF, RD, B15, conductance bridge were used for recording the respective data.

Conductometric titration was carried out by titrating 5 ml $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ Ce^{4+} , 50 ml $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Pr^{3+} or Gd^{3+} with $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ bipy or tripy, stirring the solutions for 2 min after each addition, then measuring the conductance and correcting the values due to dilution effect by multiplying the specific conductivity by the factor $\left(\frac{V_1 + V_2}{V_2}\right)$. Con-

ductometric measurements were performed using 25 ml $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ of each of Ce^{4+} and Gd^{3+} and

10 ml $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Pr^{3+} and variable concentrations of bipy or tripy keeping the total volume constant at 50 ml using double distilled water, then thermostating the solutions at 30° for 2 hr.

The spectrophotometric measurements in the ultraviolet region at 200-325 nm in the case of Ce^{4+} , Pr^{3+} and Gd^{3+} -bipy and in the ultraviolet-visible region at 200-450 nm in the case of Ce^{4+} , Pr^{3+} and Gd^{3+} -tripy were performed. The M^{n+} -bipy and M^{n+} -tripy solutions were prepared by mixing the metal ions with the ligand-buffer mixture using a blank containing the same concentrations of the ligands as in the test solutions.

Results and Discussion

Conductivity experiments :

The results of the conductometric titration and conductometric measurement give an indication of the formation of complexes having stoichiometric ratios 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 ($M^{n+} : L$). The conductance values decrease with the increase of ligand concentration as a result of the decrease in the diffusion coefficient of the diffusing particles.

Spectrophotometric measurements :

In order to find out the factors affecting the complex formation and the spectral absorbance of the complexes, effect of pH, effect of ligand concentration and effect of metal ion concentration were studied.

Effect of pH: For studying this factor, constant concentrations of metal ions and ligands ($[bipy] = 5 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $[Ce^{4+}] = [Gd^{3+}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-5} M$; $[bipy] = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $[Pr^{3+}] = 5 \times 10^{-5} M$; $[tripy] = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $[Ce^{4+}] = [Pr^{3+}] = 5 \times 10^{-5} M$, and $[tripy] = 5 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[Gd^{3+}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$) were

prepared in buffer solutions of pH 1.5-11.3. The spectral absorbances of these solutions (measured at 200-450 nm) increase with the increase of pH until they reach maxima at pH 5 (Ce⁴⁺-bipy, 305), 7.1 (Pr³⁺-bipy, 310), 5.56 (Gd³⁺-bipy, 305), 4.5 (Ce⁴⁺-tripy, 325), 4.95 (Pr³⁺-tripy, 325) and 4.0 (Gd³⁺-tripy, 340 nm), thereafter, they decrease. The increase of absorbance with pH may be due to the increased tendency for complex formation (bipy and tripy form less dissociable complexes), whereas the decrease of absorbance is due to the formation of hydroxy complexes. The bands at different pH shift due to symmetry and nonconjugation of the heterocyclic systems. Shift to lower wavelength may be due to the increased single electron delocalisation of the nonbonding orbitals of the nitrogen atom ($\pi-\pi^*$ transition), whereas shift to higher wavelength may be due to excited transition ($\pi-\pi^*$ charge transfer) of the pyridine ring. Thus, shift may be due to a coupling of $n-\pi^*$ and $\pi-\pi^*$. In general, the bands appearing within the wavelength region, 235-280 nm would be assigned to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition. The bands due to the pyridine $\pi-\pi^*$ transition change to a single band at 235 and 305 nm. These shifts could be accounted for by an easier excitation of the single electrons of the pyridine structure which in turn can be ascribed to a higher delocalisation of the electron cloud on the ring. The bands of longest wavelength can be assigned to an intramolecular charge transfer. The spectral bands of bipy, tripy and their complexes are tabulated in Table 1.

ions and ligands characters towards the formation of complexes having large concentrations of ligands.

Validity of Beer's law: Beer's law is valid for introducing bipyridyl and tripyridyl as analytical reagents for the microdetermination of 0.58-17.40 ppm Ce ($\epsilon=2 \times 10^4$), 0.23-36.42 ppm Pr ($\epsilon=5.45 \times 10^3$), 0.16-24.46 ppm Gd ($\epsilon=1.4 \times 10^3$) on using bipy, and 2.8-28 ppm Ce ($\epsilon=6 \times 10^4$), 0.2-25 ppm Pr ($\epsilon=3.5 \times 10^4$) and 0.4-10 ppm Gd ($\epsilon=12 \times 10^3$ cm²/mol) on using tripy.

Stoichiometry of the complexes: The stoichiometric composition of Ce⁴⁺, Pr³⁺ and Gd³⁺-bipy and tripy complexes determined by conductivity experiments and spectrophotometric methods (molar ratio, M.R.¹²; straight line, S.L.^{13,14}; continuous variation, C.V.^{15,16}; and limiting logarithmic, L.L.¹⁷) give 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 (M : L) ratios.

The apparent formation constant: The apparent conditional stability constants (K_f) and the free energy changes ($\Delta^\circ G$) of Ce⁴⁺, Pr³⁺, and Gd³⁺-bipy and tripy complexes are evaluated making use of the results of spectrophotometric methods¹²⁻¹⁷. Making use of the effect of pH on the spectral absorbance of the chelates, K_f can be calculated applying the equation¹⁸;

$$pH = \log \left(\frac{A}{A_L - A} \right) + pK_f + npK_i - n \log [H^+]$$

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL BANDS OF BIPYRIDYL, TRIPYRIDYL AND THEIR Ce⁴⁺-, Pr³⁺- AND Gd³⁺-CHELATES

Bipy	Tripy	Ce ⁴⁺ -bipy	Pr ³⁺ -bipy	Gd ³⁺ -bipy	Ce ⁴⁺ -tripy	Pr ³⁺ -tripy	Gd ³⁺ -tripy
235	257	305	310	305	325	325	340
280	205						
303	315						
	348						

Effect of ligand concentration: Keeping the metal ion concentration constant, the ligand concentrations were varied from one-third to five times. The absorbances increase gradually with the increase of each of [bipy] or [tripy] reaching more or less constant absorbances when sufficient excess of reagents have been added.

Effect of metal ion concentrations: The concentrations of each of bipyridyl ([bipy]= $1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$, [Ce⁴⁺]= $1.5 \times 10^{-5} - 1 \times 10^{-6} M$; [bipy]= $9 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Pr³⁺]= $1.9 \times 10^{-5} M$; and [bipy]= $6 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Gd³⁺]= $5 \times 10^{-5} M$) or tripyridyl ([tripy]= $3 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Ce⁴⁺]= $1.9 \times 10^{-5} M$; [tripy]= $9 \times 10^{-5} M$; [Pr³⁺]= $1-9 \times 10^{-5} M$; and [tripy]= $6 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Gd³⁺]= $5 \times 10^{-6} - 6 \times 10^{-5} M$) are kept constant, whereas those of the metal ions are varied. The increasing of metal ions concentration, increase the absorbance values. This may be attributed to the probable and continuous tendency for enhancing the metal

The free energy changes of the complexes can be evaluated using the equation :

$$\Delta^\circ G = - RT \ln K$$

The results of the spectral bands, stoichiometry, formation constants and the free energy changes of the chelates are recorded in Table. 1, 2 and 3. The values obtained indicate that the 1 : 4 complexes are the most stable. The orders of stability constants are Pr³⁺-> Ce⁴⁺-> Gd³⁺-bipy and tripy complexes. The tripyridyl would have been expected to form stronger chelates than the bipyridyl does due to the availability of another pyridine nitrogen, but the third pyridyl ring will experience some strain due to force bond formation (bridge) which is expected to reduce the stability.

The coordination between the ligands and the metal ions takes place through coordinate bonds between the metal ions and the nitrogen atoms of

TABLE 2—EVALUATION OF THE STOICHIOMETRY, STABILITY CONSTANTS (K_f) AND ΔG° (IN kcal mol⁻¹ AT 27°) OF Ce⁺⁺-, Pr⁺⁺- AND Gd⁺⁺-bipyridyl COMPLEXES

Method	Ratio	Ce ⁺⁺ -bipy		Pr ⁺⁺ -bipy		Gd ⁺⁺ -bipy	
		K_f	ΔG°	K_f	ΔG°	K_f	ΔG°
M. R.	1 : 1						
	1 : 2	1.16×10^{11}	16.67	5.5×10^{11}	17.60	3×10^7	10.33
	1 : 3	9.9×10^{17}	24.86	2.64×10^{19}	26.83	7.2×10^{11}	16.38
C. V.	1 : 4	1.2×10^{20}	28.79	1.9×10^{20}	32.16		
	2 : 1	3.75×10^6	7.7	4.85×10^6	7.89	1.46×10^6	7.14
	1 : 1	9.25×10^7	11.01	1.07×10^8	11.09	1.1×10^7	9.73
S. L.	1 : 2	4.67×10^{13}	17.50			1.3×10^{13}	18.12
	1 : 3			7.08×10^{10}	23.28	1.6×10^{10}	26.53
	1 : 1	5.1×10^6	7.89	6.85×10^6	8.06	5.64×10^4	6.56
L. L.	1 : 1	8.5×10^8	4.05			8.5×10^8	8.19
pH	1 : 1	1.4×10^4	5.37	1.8×10^9	12.79	4.6×10^8	5.06
						6.8×10^4	6.68

TABLE 3—EVALUATION OF THE STOICHIOMETRY, STABILITY CONSTANTS (K_f) AND ΔG° (IN kcal mol⁻¹ AT 27°) OF Ce⁺⁺-, Pr⁺⁺- AND Gd⁺⁺-tripyridyl COMPLEXES

Method	Ratio	Ce ⁺⁺ -tripy		Pr ⁺⁺ -tripy		Gd ⁺⁺ -tripy	
		K_f	ΔG°	K_f	ΔG°	K_f	ΔG°
M. R.	1 : 2			4.33×10^{11}	17.46	1.5×10^{11}	15.44
	1 : 3	1.03×10^{10}	22.12	9.06×10^{10}	23.43	2.3×10^{17}	23.99
	1 : 4	4.8×10^{21}	29.95	1.3×10^{22}	31.93	2.2×10^{22}	30.87
C. V.	1 : 1	1.05×10^6	15.93	1.65×10^6	7.21	8.34×10^4	6.8
	1 : 2	2.89×10^{11}	6.92	1×10^{14}	19.34	8.5×10^{10}	15.10
	1 : 4	7.9×10^{22}	33.02				
S. L.	1 : 1	8.5×10^8	8.19	6.85×10^6	8.06	1.54×10^5	7.17
L. L.	1 : 1	8.3×10^8	5.41	22.49	1.87		
pH	1 : 1	6.03×10^8	3.84	9.06×10^9	4.09	4.9×10^8	3.72

the pyridyl rings. This is relevant to the results of conductometric titrations and conductometric measurements which show a decrease in conductance values with the increase of bipyridyl and tripyridyl concentrations.

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